

THE CHEMISTRY OF FLUOCHLORATES. PART I. FLUOCHLORATES OF COPPER, ZINC, CADMIUM, NICKEL, COBALT, CALCIUM, STRONTIUM, BARIUM, AND LEAD

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The fluochlorates of Cu, Zn, Cd, Pb, Ba, Ca, Sr, etc. have been described. Copper, zinc, nickel, cadmium, and cobalt fluochlorates are soluble in water. The other fluochlorates are insoluble in water. From the X-ray data the nickel fluochlorate hexahydrate is found to be isomorphous with zinc monofluoroarsenate hexahydrate. Nickel and cobalt fluochlorates crystallise with six or seven molecules of water. Fluochlorates are oxidising agents. The soluble fluochlorates have been found to form mixed crystals with the corresponding sulphates, fluoroberyllates, etc.

The complex anions formed by the halogens are well known. Those formed by chlorine are COl_2^- , ClO_3^- , and ClO_4^- . It is of interest to note that no oxyfluoro complex ion of chlorine is known. Iodine forms an oxyfluoro anion, IO_2F_2^- . The difluorodioxo-iodates have been studied by Rogers and Helmholtz (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 1537).

The existence of the fluochlorates and monofluorotrioxiodates has already been established by Ray and Mitra (*Science & Culture*, 1956, 21, 379; this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 211). The fluochlorates of Cu, Zn, Cd, Ni, Co, Ca, Sr, Ba, and Pb have been studied in the present communication.

The structure of the fluochlorates in keeping with the dichlorodioxo-iodates should be as :

Hence this p^3d or p^3s hybridisation would have resulted in a more or less regular tetrahedron but for the lone pair of electrons in the 3s level. The lone pair hybridisation distorts the structure, and therefore the structure is not comparable to that of the perchlorate ion.

EXPERIMENTAL

Fluochlorates were prepared from C.P. and A.R. quality of reagents. The compounds were decomposed by fusion with alkali carbonates. The amounts of fluorine and chlorine were determined from the extract obtained by leaching the fused mass with hot water. The metals were estimated after converting the respective compounds into their corresponding sulphates by slowly heating them with H_2SO_4 (conc.) (Treadwell and Hall, "Analytical Chemistry", Vol. II).

Copper fluochlorate pentahydrate.—To a weighed amount of copper carbonate, taken in a platinum basin, 40% chloric acid was added to decompose the carbonate, last traces of which were removed by heating on a water bath. An equivalent amount of copper carbonate, taken in another platinum basin, was decomposed by addition of 40% HF. Pure CuF_2 not being sufficiently soluble in water, the excess of the acid was removed by decantation. The presence of a slight excess of hydrofluoric acid, however, has no harmful effect on the final product. To the copper fluoride, thus obtained, copper chlorate solution was added, and the mixture digested on a water bath for about 15 minutes, and then HNO_3 (conc.) was added dropwise with constant stirring till a clear solution was obtained. The solution was digested on the water bath for a further period of an hour, cooled to room temperature, and filtered to remove the insoluble impurities. The clear filtrate was kept in a vacuum desiccator over H_2SO_4 . After a few days blue crystals appeared, which were filtered under suction, washed once with water, and then with 60% ethanol, and dried in the air. (Found: Cu, 24.80; Cl, 13.78; F, 7.28. $\text{CuClO}_3\text{F} \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 24.83; Cl, 13.85; F, 7.42%). It is highly soluble in water and also in 60% ethanol.

Zinc fluochlorate heptahydrate was prepared in the way described above. It was observed that during the preparation of this compound addition of nitric acid was not necessary; the fluoride itself dissolved in a solution of zinc chlorate. (Found: Zn, 22.02; Cl, 12.00; F, 6.30. $\text{ZnClO}_3\text{F} \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Zn, 22.24; Cl, 12.07; F, 6.46%).

This compound is also highly soluble in water. The equivalent conductivity of zinc fluochlorate solutions of different concentrations was determined at 35° (Table I).

TABLE I

Conc.	..	..	M/32	M/64	M/128	M/256	*M/1024
Conduc.	..	..	50	76	95	108	124

* Conductivity at 25° became 102 (—).

From the results it appears that in solution there are only two ions:

Some amount of auto-complex formation is also indicated in a concentrated solution.

Cadmium fluochlorate 8/3 hydrate was obtained by the same method as in the case of the copper compound. On account of excessive solubility of cadmium fluochlorate a white slime, instead of crystals, was obtained. (Found: Cd, 42.56; Cl, 13.40; F, 6.96. $\text{CdClO}_3\text{F} \cdot 8/3 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cd, 42.76; Cl, 13.49; F, 7.23%).

Nickel fluochlorate heptahydrate was obtained by the method described above. (Found: Ni, 20.42; Cl, 12.30; F, 6.50. $\text{NiClO}_3\text{F} \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 20.44; Cl, 12.35; F, 6.62%). It is highly soluble in water.

Solutions of the fluochlorates, in general, do not form any precipitate with calcium chloride in the cold and do so very slowly on boiling. The fluorine atom is therefore more strongly attached to the central element in the case of $\text{ClO}_3\text{F}^{2-}$ ion than in BF_4^- , one of the most stable fluoride complex anions. This is in keeping with the fact that the Cl—F link is more covalent in character than the B—F link. This compound slowly passes into the hexahydrated form at 30° (Found: Ni, 21.82. $\text{NiClO}_3\text{F} \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 21.80%).

The powder picture of the hexahydrated nickel fluochlorate was taken. The result is shown in Table II.

TABLE II

D (in K_{α} unit)	*Intensity.	D (in K_{α} unit)	*Intensity.	D (in K_{α} unit)	*Intensity.
4.689	V. S.	2.297	W.	1.469	M. W.
4.130	S.	2.167	W.	1.376	M. W.
3.082	M. W.	2.062	M.	1.186	W.
2.894	M.	1.873	M. S.	1.116	W.
2.572	S.	1.599	M. S.	1.091	

* V. S.=very strong. S.=Strong. M. S.=Medium strong. M. W.=Medium weak. W.=Weak. V. W.=Very weak.

It is of interest to note that this compound is found to be isomorphous with $ZnAsO_3F \cdot 6H_2O$ (Mitra, *Science & Culture*, 1953, 19, 216; Ray and Mitra, unpublished data). It suggests therefore that in AsO_3F^{2-} , due to the inert nature of the 4S electrons, the hybridisation has taken place in the p^3d level. It must be noted, however, that the lone pair hybridisation taking place with arsenic and chlorine atoms in AsO_3F^{2-} and ClO_3F^{2-} respectively has resulted in a similar deformation. Further study is necessary to prove this phenomenon.

Cobalt fluochlorate heptahydrate was obtained by following the general method of preparation of the soluble fluochlorates, described above. (Found : Co, 20.40; Cl, 12.32; F, 6.50. $CoClO_3F \cdot 7H_2O$ requires Co, 20.50; Cl, 12.33; F, 6.61%).

When a concentrated solution of this compound was heated on a water bath, the hexahydrated salt crystallised out. (Found : Co, 21.80. $CoClO_3F \cdot 6H_2O$ requires Co, 21.90%).

The fluochlorates, described above, are soluble in water. It has been observed that in solution the secondary dissociation of this ion into free fluoride and chlorate ions is negligible. Addition of calcium chloride solution therefore does not result in the precipitation of calcium fluoride. All these fluochlorates form mixed crystals with the corresponding sulphates, fluoberyllates, oxyfluoborates, etc. The fluochlorates, mentioned above, form double salts with alkali metal sulphates or fluoberyllates; the molecular formulas of these double salts are similar to those of Tutton's salts. The fluochlorates like the chlorates and perchlorate exhibit oxidising properties. When the soluble fluochlorates are treated with solutions of barium chloride, calcium chloride, strontium nitrate, or lead nitrate, the sparingly soluble fluochlorates of these metals are formed. During the time of preparation of the calcium salt, a few drops of ethanol were added in order to suppress the secondary dissociation. The following fluochlorates were isolated.

Calcium fluochlorate was isolated as a very fine white precipitate. (Found : Ca, 27.85; Cl, 24.60. $CaClO_3F$ requires Ca, 28.11; Cl, 24.87%).

Strontium fluochlorate : (Found : Sr, 46.00; Cl, 18.44; F, 9.76. $SrClO_3F$ requires Sr, 46.10; Cl, 18.65; F, 10.00%).

Barium fluochlorate is the least soluble fluochlorate isolated. (Found : Ba, 57.10; Cl, 14.65; F, 7.78. $BaClO_3F$ requires Ba, 57.27; Cl, 14.78; F, 7.92%).

Lead fluochlorate was obtained by treating a concentrated solution of nickel fluochlorate with lead nitrate. (Found : Pb, 66.42; F, 6.00. $PbClO_3F$ requires Pb, 66.91; F, 6.13%).

These sparingly soluble fluochlorates have been found to be slightly more soluble in water than the corresponding sulphates.

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